

Growth and Trade in Taiwan: New Empirical Evidence from VECM Granger Causality

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Abstract

Using an extended set of variables and event-specific dummies, this study examines Taiwan's economic performance from 1981Q1 to 2023Q2. Applying VECM Granger causality tests, we find considerable support for the Export-Led Growth (ELG), Growth-Led Export (GLE), and Import-Led Growth (ILG) hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. Our findings reveal a dual role for exports: an initial positive impact on GDP that weakens over time, and a persistent stabilizing influence on GDP. The study also uncovers a long-term negative impact of imports on Taiwan's GDP despite the capital-intensive nature of its import structure. These results raise questions about potential structural issues or import-induced capital flight in Taiwan. Our data offers limited empirical support for the Growth-Led Import (GLI) hypothesis. The study also identifies a transitional phase in the relationship between imports and exports, pointing toward a potential decoupling over time.

Keywords: International Trade, VECM, Export, Import, Taiwan.

JEL Classifications: F41, B17, C32

1. Introduction

International trade's influence on economic development has evolved through centuries of economic thought. The Mercantilist perspective, which dominated the early thoughts on trade, emphasized the importance of accumulating wealth through a positive balance of trade. This view was later challenged by the groundbreaking work of Adam Smith and David Ricardo, who introduced the concepts of absolute and comparative advantage, respectively.

In the 20th century, the focus of trade theories expanded to include new dimensions. The Heckscher-Ohlin theory, for instance, emphasized the role of factor endowments in shaping trade

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patterns. Midway through the century, attention began to turn to the multifaceted effects of exports on economic well-being. This led to important scholarly contributions, such as those by Emery (1967), who probed the links between accelerated export growth and expansive economic development.

The latter part of the century witnessed the rise of New Trade Theory, signaling a more dynamic phase in trade thinking. Notable economists like Krugman (1980) enriched the field by introducing contemporary concepts such as increasing returns to scale, product differentiation, and monopolistic competition. These ideas helped construct a more nuanced and adaptive understanding of global trade dynamics. Recent decades have seen continued expansion in the scope of trade theories. Further research, including works by Edwards (1998) and Frankel and Romer (1999) have further articulated the fundamental role that international trade plays in shaping a nation's economic trajectory. They emphasize not only the direct effects of trade on economic metrics but also its influence on structural adjustments and technological adaptation.

In the global context, Taiwan serves as an instructive case study for international trade theories. Taiwan's economic narrative over the past four decades highlights its adaptive agility in responding to the demands and opportunities of global trade. Boasting an average of 8% GDP growth rate and a leap in per capita income from \$4130 in the 1980s to \$32756 in 2022, Taiwan stands as a prime example of what sound trade and economic policies can achieve.

Much of this success was facilitated by policy measures like trade liberalization introduced in 1984. The policy slashed effective tariff rates to a current low of 1.14% (Customs Administration, Taiwan R.O.C., 2023). Such strategic choices were made viable by Taiwan's managed float exchange rate system, effective since 1987, and its calculated engagement with trade partners, notably China. After establishing indirect trade with China in 1993 and direct trade in 2002, Taiwan saw a considerable boost in bilateral trade volumes (Liu et al., 2022).

Taiwan holds the 5th largest market economy in Asia and the 17th largest globally by PPP. A leader in technology, Taiwan ranks closely to Poland and Sweden in nominal GDP and has a significant presence in the ICT industry (Britannica, 2023). Data from 2021 shows Taiwan as the 16th largest exporter and 17th largest importer worldwide, with notable year-on-year growth in both exports (29.4%) and imports (33.2%) (Government Portal of Republic of China, Taiwan., 2022). Continuing this trend, 2022 saw a 7.4% increase in exports to \$479.4 billion and a 12.1% increase in imports to \$428.0 billion despite the global economic downturn caused by the

COVID-19 pandemic (Tang et al., 2021). The New Southbound Policy, membership in WTO since 2002 and economic cooperation agreements with various nations, underline Taiwan's commitment to deepening international relations and solidifying its position as a major supplier across various industrial sectors (Chien et al., 2020).

In trade distribution, Mainland China and Hong Kong lead, accounting for 38.8% of exports and 20.0% of imports. They are followed by ASEAN countries (16.8% exports, 12.6% imports), Japan (7.0% exports, 12.8% imports), the United States (15.7% exports, 10.6% imports), and Europe (8.6% exports, 11.9% imports).

Table 1 shows that Taiwan's top exports are largely in electronics, with Electronic Integrated Circuits making up 38.4%. The varied nature of imports suggests a balanced economic structure.

Table 1. Exports and Imports of Leading Export Commodities in 2022

Item	Exports, %	Imports, %
Parts of Electronic Products	41.7	23.0
- Electronic Integrated Circuits	38.4	-
Information, Communication and Audio-video Products	13.5	6.6
Base Metals and Articles of Base Metal	7.7	6.6
Machinery	6.0	11.5
Plastics & Rubber and Articles Thereof	5.4	-
Chemicals	4.9	8.4
Mineral Products	4.1	19.7
Vehicles, Aircraft, Vessels and Associated Transport Equipment	3.5	3.4
Electrical Machinery Products	-	3.4

Figure 1 shows the temporal evolution of Taiwan's GDP, exports, and imports from 1981 to 2023. The data shows a decline in imports and exports in 2009, followed by a steady period that lasts until a dip in 2019. Interestingly, from 2020 onward, both imports and exports exhibit rapid growth, even during the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. GDP demonstrates consistent upward movement throughout the entire timeframe.

While Taiwan's remarkable growth and active participation in international trade make it a compelling subject for academic inquiry, existing literature presents inconsistent findings. On one hand, studies by Xu (1998) and Mahadevan & Suardi (2008) affirm the Export-Led Growth (ELG) hypothesis, suggesting that export promotion significantly contributes to its economic expansion. On the other hand, works such as those by Chang et al. (2000) refute the ELG hypothesis, and instead underscore the Growth-Led Exports (GLE) model, suggesting that

Taiwan's economic growth fuels its export activities. Furthermore, a subset of research by Xu (1996), Tang et al. (2015), Yang & Wu, (2015) provides mixed evidence, introducing complexity into the discourse. Additional studies by Thangavelu & Rajaguru (2004) have even proposed the Import-Led Growth (ILG) as another paradigm.

Given the varied findings in existing research, this study aims to clarify the relationship between exports, imports, and economic growth in Taiwan. Our main focus is on the ELG hypothesis, but we also examine GLE and ILG. The main research question is: What is the causal relationship between exports, imports, and GDP in Taiwan, and how do these relationships evolve over time?

This paper distinguishes itself from the existing literature in several key aspects. Firstly, it incorporates Gross Capital Formation as an additional explanatory variable, thereby broadening the scope to include domestic investment behavior. Secondly, the study employs the Producer Price Index (PPI) instead of the commonly used Consumer Price Index (CPI) to control for inflation. This approach allows for the examination of cost pressures on producers and may offer new insights. To enhance the rigor of the analysis, the time frame extends from the first quarter of 1981 to the second quarter of 2023, encompassing a range of economic cycles and events. To augment the robustness of research, event-specific dummy variables that signify landmark economic events such as dot-com bubble, the 2008 financial crisis, industry structural shifts from 2002 to 2015, and the economic disruptions triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic were included.

Figure 1. Trends in Taiwan's GDP, Exports, Imports (1981-2023) in Million NTD

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a comprehensive review of the literature relevant to the subject matter. Section 3 outlines the methodology employed. Section 4 presents the empirical results, and Section 5 concludes the study.

2. Literature review

The relationship between trade and economic growth has garnered significant academic interest, leading to a substantial body of literature. This research is often framed around four key hypotheses: ELG, GLE, ILG, and Growth-Led Import (GLI). Of these, the ELG hypothesis has been particularly well-studied. It suggests that countries can boost their economic growth by focusing on exports. The impact of trade on GDP can be either direct, through increased demand, or indirect, by enhancing productivity via specialization. Empirical studies, such as those by Helpman and Krugman (1987), have extended this understanding by linking export growth to efficient resource allocation, increased capacity utilization, and technological innovation. Additionally, increased exports can facilitate the import of advanced goods, further contributing to productivity Bhagwati (1988), Giles and Williams (2000).

However, empirical foundation for the ELG hypothesis is not universally strong. Although early works by Balassa (1978) and Feder (1983) reported correlations between export growth and economic performance, they did not establish a causal relationship. This limitation was

partly addressed by Jung and Marshall (1985), employed Granger causality tests to explore the causality between output and exports across multiple Asian countries. Their study revealed a unidirectional causality from exports to output in Indonesia and Turkey. On the other hand, they found that output led to exports in Iran, Korea, Pakistan, Taiwan, and Thailand. Similar results were obtained by Darrat (1986), further corroborated these findings in a Taiwan-centric study, revealing a one-way causality flowing from output to exports.

A wave of methodological critiques followed these initial studies. Concerns included inappropriate statistical techniques, such as arbitrary lag length selection and misapplication of F-test statistics (Marin, 1992). Ghartey (1993) echoed these concerns, emphasizing issues with the two-variable model specification commonly used. Toda and Yamamoto (1995) and Zapata and Rambaldi (1997) extended these critiques, advocating for more rigorous analytical frameworks. Subsequent research, such as work by Riezman et al. (1996), began to broaden the scope to consider the role of imports alongside exports. Xu (1996) further refined the methodology, employing Engle-Granger cointegration and Granger causality tests to assess the causality between output and exports. The research identified a one-way causality from exports to output in India, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, and the Philippines. Conversely, in Sri Lanka, causality was established from output to exports. And bidirectional causality was observed in Hong Kong, Taiwan, Thailand, and Turkey.

Building on this, Shan and Sun (1998) broadened the analytical lens to incorporate additional variables such as imports, investment, energy consumption, and labor force. Their study revealed a unidirectional causality from exports to output in Taiwan and a bidirectional causality in Hong Kong and Korea. Subsequent research has generated mixed findings. For instance, Vohra (2001) identified strong positive effects of exports on economic growth in five Asian countries. Later research by Choong et al. (2005) corroborated ELG support in China, Hong Kong, Korea, the Philippines, and Thailand. Love and Chandra (2005) presented a nuanced picture in South Asia, reporting mixed outcomes. Awokuse (2005) discovered a bi-directional causal relationship between real exports and real GDP growth in Korea. Further contributing to this ongoing debate, Parida and Sahoo (2007) pinpointed a one-way causality running from exports to output in a study covering four South Asian countries. Similar conclusions were reached by Tan et al. (2007) in Korea and Taiwan, though they also found a two-way causality in Thailand and an opposite causal relationship in Singapore.

Dash (2009) and Zang and Baimbridge (2012) explored similar themes but in different contexts. Dash reported one-way causality from exports to output in India, while Zang and Baimbridge found evidence supporting the ELG hypothesis in Japan. On the contrary, Tiwari and Mutascu (2011) did not find any causal link between output and exports in their study on four Asian countries. Hye et al. (2013) expanded the geographical scope to South Asia and found one-way causality from exports to output in Bhutan and Sri Lanka. However, their study found no causality in Bangladesh, India, Nepal, and Pakistan.

Tang et al. (2015) applied Johansen's cointegration and Granger causality tests to analyze output, exports, and real exchange rates. Their study revealed a unidirectional causality running from output to exports in Korea and Taiwan, alongside a bidirectional causality in Hong Kong and Singapore. In a complementary vein, Yang and Wu (2015) applied Johansen's cointegration and Granger causality to examine the relationship between output and exports. Their analysis supported the existence of a bidirectional causality between these variables in China and Taiwan. Extending this line of inquiry, Tang and Abosedra (2019) utilized balanced panel data from 23 Asian countries to test the export-led growth (ELG) hypothesis, focusing on the role of logistics performance. Their findings not only confirmed the validity of the ELG hypothesis across all countries examined but also underscored the importance of logistics performance as a conditional factor for economic growth. Usman and Bashir (2022) identified a detrimental effect of import growth on China's GDP. Complementing these findings, Zhu et al. (2022) studied the relationship between GDP, exports, and exchange rates in Asian countries. Their results suggest a significant nexus between exchange rates and exports, reinforcing both the ELG and GLE hypotheses.

In light of the diverse findings and methodological advancements in the literature, it is evident that the relationship between trade and economic growth remains a complex and contested subject. While the ELG hypothesis has dominated much of the discourse, emerging evidence also highlights the importance of considering imports and other economic variables.

3. Data and Methodology

3.1 Data

This study undertakes a time-series analysis using quarterly data, spanning the period from 1981Q1 to 2023Q2. Unlike prior studies that focus predominantly on Gross Domestic Product

(*GDP*), merchandise exports (*E*), and merchandise imports (*M*) as proxies for economic variables (Hye et al., 2013), the analytical framework of this research is expanded to incorporate Gross Capital (*GCap*). This acts as a proxy for domestic investment and addresses potential omitted variable bias. Data for these variables are sourced from the National Bureau of Statistics of Taiwan and converted to current U.S. dollars using prevailing exchange rates, thereby enhancing comparability. Consistent with Bahmani-Oskooee and Economidou (2008), all variables are transformed into natural logarithmic scales for empirical analysis. Additional index is included to increase the robustness of the findings: Producer Price Index (*PPI*), which is adjusted on a quarterly basis to account for inflationary factors. To control for the influence of significant economic events, dummy variables are also incorporated, representing occurrences such as the dot-com bubble, the financial crisis, and the COVID-19 pandemic.

3.2 Methodology

This study explores the relationship between exports, imports, and GDP in Taiwan by examining four economic hypotheses: ELG, GLE, ILG, and GLI. It is anticipated that both exports and imports will be significant determinants of Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

To mitigate the risk of spurious regressions, as stated by Granger (1974), the stationarity of the time-series variables is first verified. Both the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Elliott, Rothenberg, and Stock (ERS) test unit root tests are employed. The ERS test (1996a), an extension of the ADF test, utilizes a point-optimal bandwidth to determine the optimal number of lags in the model. It also accounts for serial correlation in the error term by employing a Newey-West heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) estimator. Using these tests provides a robust check on the stationarity of the variables. Both tests revealed non-stationarity across all series at levels.

Upon confirming the stationarity of the time-series variables at first-differences, this study proceeds to explore long-term relationships between them. We employ the Johansen-Hendry-Juselius cointegration technique, drawing upon established conventions from Johansen (1995), Hendry and Juselius (2001), and Juselius (2006). This technique aids in determining the number of cointegrating vectors among endogenous variables. Following guidelines from Lütkepohl (2005), the maximum lag length considered for quarterly data ranges between 1 and 12 quarters. To identify the most suitable lag structure for Vector Error-Correction Model

(VECM), we rely on the Hannan-Quinn information criterion. The optimal number of lags is determined to be 5, as indicated by the lowest HQ value at this lag length.

Given that our variables are cointegrated, it becomes essential to employ a VECM to study the dynamic relationships (Juselius, 2006):

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \Pi Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \Gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + D_t + \varepsilon_t.$$

Here, α is a constant term, ΠY_{t-1} is the error correction term, Δ represents the first difference operator, Y_t is a vector containing the endogenous variables, Π, Γ_i are matrices capturing long-term and short-term dynamics respectively, D_t is a vector of dummy variables. Finally, ε_t is the vector of error terms.

Unlike a conventional VAR model, which is influenced only by short-term lagged variables, the VECM introduces long-term dynamics through the error correction term, offering a more comprehensive framework for Granger causality (Maddala & Kim, 1999). To ascertain the validity of the model, several diagnostic tests are employed. These include the LM Test for serial correlation (Breusch, 1978) and the White heteroskedasticity test for constant variance in the model's residuals (White, 1980). The LM Test confirms no serial correlation in the residuals at the 5% significance level. The White heteroskedasticity test establishes constant variance in the model's residuals. Satisfying these criteria enables further analysis through the block-wise Granger causality tests (Lütkepohl, 2005), which consider both short-term and long-term dynamics.

Impulse Response Functions (Sims, 1980) are also generated to trace the effect of a one standard deviation shock to one of the innovations on current and future values of the endogenous variables. Bootstrap methods are used to compute standard errors, thus enhancing the robustness of our findings (Efron, 1992). The Impulse Response analysis covers periods up to 12 quarters, allowing for both short-term and medium-term effects to be studied.

4. Results and Discussion

First, the study assesses the time-series properties of the data using the ADF and ERS unit root tests. Both tests aim to reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity. Table 2 displays the outcomes of the ADF and ERS unit root tests for both levels and first differences. The findings indicate that the variables are non-stationary at their levels but achieve stationarity upon first

differencing, making them integrated of order $I(1)$. The results of the current study align well with seminal work by Nelson and Plosser (1982), who asserted that most macroeconomic variables exhibit non-stationarity at their levels but achieve stationarity upon first differencing.

Table 2. Stationarity tests

Variable	ADF in Levels t-statistics	ADF in First- differences t-statistics	ERS in Levels P-statistics	ERS in First- differences P-statistics
GDP, USD	0.844	-6.739***	449.152	0.314**
Exports, USD	0.146	-7.739***	129.617	0.291***
Imports, USD	-0.211	-7.213***	83.279	0.003***
PPI	-0.445	-9.634***	18.797	0.196***
Gross capital formation, USD	0.396	-6.554***	83.329	0.0448***

Note: The reported results were estimated with a constant and linear trend, and asterisks denote statistical significance: * – 10%, ** – 5%, and *** – 1%. The critical values for the ADF tests are based on (MacKinnon, 1996) and the (Elliott et al., 1996b) test on stationarity.

Assuming that the cointegrating relationship incorporates a constant term, Johansen-Hendry-Juselius Trace and Max-Eigenvalue tests were performed. The outcomes are detailed in Table 3. Both tests reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration at the 0.05 significance level, thereby implying the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables under study.

Table 3. Johansen-Hendry-Juselius cointegration test

Null hypotheses	Eigenvalue	Trace test		Max-eigenvalue test	
		Trace Statistic	p-value	Max-Eigen Statistic	p-value
$r = 0$	0.242	91.848***	0.000	39.529***	0.002
$r \leq 1$	0.146	46.659	0.065	31.553	0.083
$r \leq 2$	0.069	20.847	0.367	13.677	0.585
$r \leq 3$	0.038	9.220	0.345	0.0812	0.566
$r \leq 4$	0.017	2.846	0.092	0.017	0.092

Note: r is the hypothesized number of cointegrating equations. *** denotes rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration at a 1% significance level

The normalized cointegrating equation for Taiwan's GDP is elucidated in Table 4. In the long-term perspective, a 1% increase in GDP is associated with a 0.837% increase in exports and a 0.657% increase in Gross Capital Formation. These results are in line with the literature; for instance, Malhotra and Kumari (2016) identified a similar positive association in China but a negative one in Japan and South Korea. Our findings also reinforce seminal works such as Tyler (1981), which highlighted the significance of capital formation in economic growth.

Table 4. Normalized coefficients for cointegrating GDP equation

	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic
$\log(GDP(-1))$	1.00	-	-
$\log(E(-1))$	-0.837***	0.093	8.995
$\log(M(-1))$	0.462***	0.145	3.174
$\log(GCap(-1))$	-0.657***	0.076	-8.643
$PPI(-1)$	0.007***	0.001	5.703
C	-1.278	-	-

Note: *** denote statistical significance at 1%.

Our data further corroborates the findings of Lewer and Berg (2003), who showed that a one percentage point rise in export growth relates to a 0.2% increase in economic growth. On the other hand, higher domestic production levels, as indicated by rising GDP, could be associated with a decline in import activity in Taiwan. As measured by the PPI, inflationary pressures are mildly reduced with economic growth. This effect is in line with McCarthy (2000), who found that the impact of exchange rates and import prices on domestic PPI is relatively modest but stronger in economies with a larger import share.

Following the identification of cointegration among the variables, a VECM with one cointegrated relation was estimated. The diagnostic tests indicate that the model satisfies the critical assumptions of homoscedasticity and absence of serial correlation in the residuals. The White test yielded a χ^2 statistic of 866.347 with a p-value of 0.083. The Lagrange Multiplier test for serial correlation was conducted at lag 5 and for lags 1 to 5. The Rao F-statistics were 1.214 and 1.156, with p-values of 0.219 and 0.142, respectively.

Table 5. VECM Granger causality test results

Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
Dependent variable ΔGDP			
ΔE	16.059	5	0.007***
ΔM	13.100	5	0.022**
$\Delta GCap$	14.108	5	0.015**
ΔPPI	0.824	5	0.975
ALL	38.768	20	0.007***
Dependent variable ΔE			
ΔGDP	11.473	5	0.043**
ΔM	5.420	5	0.367
$\Delta GCap$	8.825	5	0.116
ΔPPI	9.732	5	0.083*
ALL	42.503	20	0.002***
Dependent variable ΔM			
ΔGDP	10.135	5	0.072*
ΔE	11.994	5	0.035**
$\Delta GCap$	3.299	5	0.654
ΔPPI	17.262	5	0.004***

ALL	79.737	20	0.001***
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Note: $\Delta GDP, \Delta E, \Delta M, \Delta GCap$ denote the first differences of the logarithmic values of the GDP, exports, imports, and gross capital formation, respectively, ***, ** and * denote statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

For the Granger causality tests in Table 5, causality is observed from exports, imports, and gross capital formation to GDP. However, the PPI variable does not Granger-cause GDP evidenced by a p-value of 0.975, suggesting that inflationary pressures have a negligible immediate effect on GDP. In turn, GDP shows Granger causality to exports (p-value 0.043), but not to imports or gross capital formation. Furthermore, imports and PPI are significantly related (p-value 0.004), indicating that changes in import levels may be highly sensitive to inflationary pressures. Policymakers should consider this relationship when crafting import policies, especially if inflation control is a priority.

Figure 2. Impulse response functions

In summary, our findings yield compelling evidence in favor of the ELG hypothesis, validated by a p-value of 0.007. The GLE hypothesis garners moderate support, indicated by a p-value of 0.043. The ILG hypothesis also finds notable support with a p-value of 0.022, though it's crucial to note that the relationship is negative. Conversely, the GLI hypothesis does not find empirical backing, as evidenced by a p-value of 0.072.

Figure 2 supports the cointegration results, showing long-term equilibrium adjustments among these variables. Focusing on the response of $\log(GDP)$ to its own shocks, the data reveals a form of self-sustaining growth.

Our results show a dual role for trade variables in Taiwan's economic performance. On one hand, $\log(Exports)$ initially boost $\log(GDP)$, thus supporting ELG hypothesis. This surge could be ascribed to increased global demand for Taiwanese goods. However, this beneficial impact weakens and becomes negative from period 4 onward. This aligns with studies on other

economies, such as Mexico, where Souza and Gómez-Ramírez (2018) found that increased exports did not sustain long-term GDP growth. The implication for Taiwan is cautionary: a burgeoning export sector may not yield long-term economic advantages.

On the other hand, results validate the GLE hypothesis, showing a persistent positive influence of $\log(\text{Exports})$ on $\log(\text{GDP})$ throughout the observed periods. The response rate begins at 0.031 and peaks at 0.061 by period 5. Remarkably, the sensitivity does not decline below the initial level of 0.031, indicating that exports persist as a stabilizing variable in Taiwan's economic matrix. These findings align with Pretorius et al. (2021), who emphasized the importance of economic openness and export market dynamics in fostering economic resilience, and resonates with the observations of Briguglio (2016), who would attribute such resilience to effective policy measures that enable an economy to recover from external shocks. Such resilience is notably valuable for a small, open economy that is susceptible to global economic volatilities.

Supplementing these insights, the autoregressive feature in exports, which initially show robustness with a rate of 0.042 but diminish over time. This pattern aligns with Montobbio and Rampa's (2005) observations about the challenges of sustaining export gains in the face of structural and technological shifts.

Turning to the import side, our VECM results indicate that the GLI hypothesis lacks strong empirical support, evidenced by a p-value of 0.072. Despite this, the observed data shows a phase where rising GDP corresponds with increased import activity.

The impact of imports on Taiwan's GDP starts to decline from period 3. This trend invites a re-examination of consumption behaviors, as increased imports may detract from domestic production. Given the data in Table 1, a dominant share of imports is in parts of electronic products, mineral products and machinery. While a capital-intensive import structure could theoretically augment domestic production capacity in the long run (Cavallo & Landry, 2010), our study shows a long-term negative impact on GDP. This finding is at variance with research on other economies. For example, Kim et al. (2009) found that in Korea, imports had a significantly positive impact on GDP growth, attributed not only to competitive pressures from consumer goods but also to technological transfers from capital goods. Our study thus raises a critical question: Could the observed negative relationship with GDP in Taiwan be indicative of

a structural issue or perhaps an import-induced capital flight that diverges from trends observed in other economies like the U.S. and Korea?

Concurrently, our data shows that the relationship between imports and exports is initially complementary but turns negative in later periods. This observation aligns with work by Fan et al. (2019) and points to a potential decoupling of export and import activities over time. The decline and stabilization in the self-reinforcing nature of imports may indicate either market adjustments or effective policy measures, contributing to a new equilibrium in import activities.

We contend that our approach, including more variables and covering an extended timeframe, provides a more holistic understanding of Taiwan's economic dynamics. Our findings are in contrast to the unidirectional causality from exports to output in Taiwan found by Shan and Sun (1998), Tan et al. (2007) and Tang et al. (2015) and aligns more closely with bidirectional relationships found by Yang and Wu (2015). Our study suggests that Taiwan may experience negative GDP impacts from increased imports, marking a departure from patterns observed in South Asian countries by Hue et al. (2013). The detrimental effect of import growth on Taiwan's GDP is more in line with Usman and Bashir (2022) who found a negative effect of import growth on China's GDP.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study offers substantial evidence in support of the Export-Led Growth (ELG), Import-Led Growth (ILG), and Growth-Led Export (GLE) hypotheses in the context of Taiwan. It distinctly finds a lack of empirical backing for the Growth-Led Import (GLI) hypothesis, as indicated by a p-value of 0.072. Notably, our results validate the ELG hypothesis but also reveal its limitations: exports positively influence GDP initially but this effect weakens over time. This trend warrants cautious optimism for Taiwan and suggests the need for a diversified economic strategy, in alignment with findings from other global economies.

The study also confirms the GLE hypothesis, indicating that exports serve as a consistent stabilizing force in Taiwan's economic landscape. This resilience is especially crucial for Taiwan, given its susceptibility to global economic fluctuations. These observations echo existing literature, reinforcing the importance of strategic policy measures in enhancing economic stability.

Turning to the import sector, the relationship with GDP undergoes a notable shift—from an initial positive correlation to a negative one. This finding diverges from trends observed in countries like Korea and calls for deeper inquiry into the structural or policy-driven factors influencing Taiwan's import-GDP dynamics. Moreover, our data exposes a fluctuating relationship between imports and exports, warranting closer scrutiny of Taiwan's trade policies.

Recommendations for Future Research

Building on the findings of this study, several avenues for future research emerge. First, given the fluctuating role of exports in Taiwan's economic performance subsequent research should focus on dissecting Taiwan's export basket. Such approach can clarify how different types of exports contribute to economic performance. This could help policy-makers better leverage the strengths of individual sectors in line with both the ELG and GLE hypothesis.

Second, the divergent results on the impact of imports on GDP in Taiwan require further investigation. Future research should consider a time-series analysis that focuses on micro-level data for specific import categories, such as capital goods, consumer goods, and intermediary goods. Delving into these categories can illuminate whether local production capabilities, technological transfers, or trade agreements are influencing this relationship.

Third, our study underscores a transitional phase in the correlation between imports and exports. Investigating this phenomenon in detail – perhaps through the lens of evolving global supply chains or shifts in domestic policies – can offer insights into why this relationship turns negative over time. Understanding this transition is pivotal for anticipating future economic scenarios and guiding adjustments in trade policies.

Fourth, aligning with global emphasis on sustainable growth, future research should broaden its scope beyond strictly economic metrics to include indicators of social well-being and sustainability. For Taiwan, an economy highly susceptible to global fluctuations, incorporating social resilience indicators into a comprehensive evaluation could provide a more holistic understanding of the nation's economic stability.

Data Availability

The datasets used and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declarations

The authors declare no competing interests.

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